

**US-SAUDI RELATIONSHIP IN THE WAKE OF SAUDI VISION 2030: A
STUDY TO FIND THE POST-OIL US-SAUDI RELATIONSHIP
DETERMINANTS**

by

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ABSTRACT

Saudi Arabia and the United States are different regions with dissimilar religions, cultures, and approaches. These countries are far from each other but maintain effective and bilateral relations. The Saudi-US alliance was initiated in the 1930s in relevance to the oil for security trade. With the evolving world, external factors are also changing. For instance, with Saudi Arabia, the oil process and, in response, the crown Prince of Saudi Arabia- Prince Mohammed Bin Salman, initiated an economic agenda known as "Saudi vision 2030" The Saudi vision 2030 is accompanied by a national transformation plan that would diversify the economic growth of the country and reduce its oil dependency. The Saudi vision will also enhance and promote the country's long-term economic growth and sustainability. The study aims to analyze the post-oil Saudi and US relations and their determinants. The current study utilized an epistemological paradigm and qualitative method to present data collected from literature sources. The research findings highlight the future of Saudi-US relations in a very comprehensive way, analyze the literature sources, and derive effective results for the research questions.

Keywords: Saudi-US alliance, Saudi Vision 2030, foreign relations, oil dependency

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CHAPTER 1- INTRODUCTION

The introductory chapter contains the research background, problem statement, aims and objectives, research questions, and dissertation structure.

Research background

Saudi Arabia and the United States have bilateral relations in which both enjoy benefits. The alliance forged by President Franklin Roosevelt and King Abdul Aziz in 1945 is based on mutualism; hence, both countries benefit from the contiguity dependent on oil provision for security. However, relations between the two countries are not without crises and challenges. An instance is that both countries have differing opinions on the major Middle East and gulf region issues. The research study will analyze the history of Saudi Arab and US relationships to identify the determinants.

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is in the Middle East and Gulf area, and the country's location might be considered a contributing factor to the political issues it experiences. As Malley (2019) describes it, issues like perceived complacency with Islamic extremism and pressures for social reform. In addition to the political crisis, the U.S. Congress passed the JASTA ("*Justice against Sponsors of Terrorism Act*") bill, which further affected the bilateral relations between both countries. The regulation bill enables the people of the United States to sue the government of Saudi Arabia for its alleged part and association with the 9/11 terror attack. However, despite the challenges, both countries have maintained healthy relations based on mutualism and benefits.

Salameh et al. (2016) indicate that Saudi Arabia has developed since discovering oil in the Dammam oil well. However, the country's economy still

depends on its oil revenue. The region has long been regarded as one of the biggest oil exporters among the Gulf countries. Still, seventy-eight years later, the economy depends on oil revenues, which make up 90% of the monetary value. Until recently, the government realized the need to expand its dependency and incoming sources. In response to this, Faudot (2019) stated that Saudi Arabia embarked on economic reform and a shift from reliance on oil exports. To cope with the new development, Saudi Arabia launched "*Saudi Vision 2030*," which aims to expand the country's non-oil sector and eliminate unemployment and economic crisis.

The core logic underpinning the relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States is that the United States provides military protection to Saudi Arabia in exchange for a reliable oil supply. The relationship has been critical because the alliance has faced several challenges in the past decades. It survived the 1973 oil embargo and the terrorist attack on 9/11. It also rebounded from the Khashoggi murder amidst widespread outcry over the war in Yemen. This research will provide details on both countries' challenges like the 9/11 terrorism attack, the Jamaal Khashoggi murder and their relationship history to identify the determinants and analyses the pattern of their relationship. Through the identification of the determinants and their behaviors in past disputes, the future of their relationship can be predicted.

Both Saudi Arabia and the United States have bilateral relations, and both enjoy the fruits of their friendship. The research will identify the determinants that have assisted in maintaining the bilateral relationship between both countries and highlight factors that can improve their relations during a crisis. This includes factors through which they managed to continue their alliance during challenges and crises. It

will further analyze the historical timeline of Saudi-US relationships, which includes political events and controversies. Furthermore, the impact Saudi Vision 2030 will have on US-Saudi relations will be studied.

Problem Statement

Saudi Arabia is making spirited efforts to enhance economic strategies and adapt to technological revolution. The Saudi vision 2030 is a prime example of this and, there is a push to develop a cordial relationship for effective bilateral trade between countries of interest. President Barack Obama signed a deal with Iran in the wake of the oil trade-however; the emergence of ISIS in the equation has seen the oil trade among these countries sour. The fact remains that the primary interests among other things are security, the preservation of stability, and the prosperity of the Gulf region. The study will analyze the policy changes in Saudi Arabia, and the strategies in place to aid the shift from a dependence on oil to a non-oil economy through official web pages and trusted online sources.

Aim and objectives of the research

The research aims to study and identify the determinants of the Saudi-US relationship post-oil reforms. It also aims to analyze the relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States in the wake of Vision 2030.

The objectives of the current research study are

- To critically analyze the scope and approach of the Saudi Vision 2030 using an interpretivism philosophy and epistemological paradigm .This helps to portray gleaned information in a comprehensive manner.

- To evaluate the impacts of the Saudi vision on the Saudi Arabia's oil-dependent economy using non-empirical research based on a systematic review of published and related publications
- To investigate the post-oil reform relationship between the United States and Saudi Arabia in order to establish how the oil reform will have an impact on the relationship between the two countries.

Research questions

The research questions narrow down the study area and give a direction for the investigation in alignment with the research objectives. The research questions of the current research are:

- How Saudi Vision 2030 will transform Saudi Arabia's oil-dependent economy?
- What are the determinants of Saudi Arabia and US relations apart from oil and arms reforms?
- How will Saudi Vision 2030 influence the relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States?

Thesis statement

The thesis statement of the current research study is “What are the determinants shaping the post-oil relationship and how will these determinants impact the relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States?”

Structure of the research

The current dissertation is a non-empirical research but follows a standard structure: introduction, literature review, methodology, results, and conclusion.

The chapters of the dissertation highlight the garnered knowledge about the selected topic. Chapter one contains the research background, problem statements, aims and objectives, research questions, and research structure. The introduction is significant for understanding the reason behind the topic selection and narrowing down the research area in the selected topic.

Also, the chapter gives a highlight or glimpse of the entire dissertation. Chapter two, the literature review, provides a critical analysis of the evolution of the Saudi-US relationship and highlights the changes the United States and Saudi alliances encountered. The analysis also gives information about the patterns and determinants of Saudi-US relationships. The third chapter, the research methodology, points out the research methods, choices, and data collection techniques. This chapter also contains technical information about the research, which includes reliability and validity-the practical methodology aids in effective data collection and analysis, which is the core of every research study. Chapter four contains analyzed information from the selected sources through which the research questions are answered, and the research aims are achieved. The final chapter of the dissertation is the conclusion and recommendation. It highlights the dissertation's key findings and evaluates them to indicate the limitations and future recommendations for the research. The conclusion is the shorter version of the entire dissertation. It summarizes the details of every chapter and the key findings of the research study. Aside from the essential five chapters, the dissertation includes an abstract, TOC (Table of content), and references.

CHAPTER 2—LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

In the current research project, the literature review will analyze the development of Saudi and American reliance on one another, the challenges faced by the Saudi-American alliance, and the shift in their relationship due to those challenges.

The origins and evolution of the U.S.–Saudi alliance

The early 1930s witnessed the beginning of a strategic partnership between the United States of America and Saudi Arabia. In 1928, Saudi Arabia launched a program intending to cultivate relationships with nations worldwide. According to the editors of CFR.org (2018), the United Kingdom was the first country to formally recognize Saudi Arabia and support the Kingdom with security and allies. Hence, diplomatic ties between the United States and Saudi Arabia were not established until 1931, when the two countries signed a deal to trade oil.

For almost a century, the United States of America and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia have maintained a solid relationship founded on mutual respect and common interests. Following establishing diplomatic ties in 1933 and opening the United States Embassy in Jeddah in 1944 (the embassy was relocated to Riyadh in 1984), the expansion of the oil deal, which granted the United States authority to locate potential sites for oil and gas drilling and extraction from Saudi territories, was a significant factor in strengthening the alliance between the two nations. The Saudi monarch permitted firms based in the United States to undergo oil exploration from al-Hasa, located in the eastern region of Saudi Arabia (Morse and Richard, 2002). According

to Bronson (2005), the Arabian American oil company Aramco made the initial discovery of oil in 1938. The discovery and subsequent exploration helped strengthen both the economy of Saudi Arabia and that of the United States, which in turn cleared the way for more balanced ties between the two countries and the formation of an oil-for-security reform program.

According to Blanchard (2009), the United States and Saudi Arabia had a close working connection from the beginning of Saudi Arabia's oil production in 1933. This link was primarily because both countries benefited greatly from the oil industry. A partnership between Texaco (known as Standard Oil and the Texas Oil Company) and Saudi Arabia was established in 1936. As a direct consequence of this partnership, the firm known as ARAMCO (Arabian American Oil Company) came into existence. Based on the relationship with established United States oil corporations like Chevron, Dow Chemical, and ExxonMobil, CFR.org Editors (2018) noted that with their help, Saudi Arabia gradually bought out its foreign shareholders, and became the most significant oil exporter in the world (CFR.org Editors, 2018).

In addition to having the most fabulous crude oil reserves in the world, Saudi Arabia also produces over 10.7 million barrels of oil every day. On average, 7.43 million barrels are exported out of 10.7 million produced daily. According to the editors of CFR.org (2018), the magnitude and scope of a country's oil exports impact the energy market and the oil production process at the international level. However, on the international market, oil prices are dramatically impacted by the "Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries," sometimes known as OPEC. The Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) acts as a central banker by attempting to

modify or stabilize the global oil market and prices. From its inception in 1961, the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) has endeavored to exert control over the oil market, which directly impacts consumers in the United States. Since the 1970s, the United States has prioritized its foreign policy to defend oil-producing nations. This commitment to protecting oil-producing nations remains a cornerstone of US foreign policy (CFR.org Editors, 2018).

Oil exports and trade between Saudi Arabia and the United States were disrupted in 1973 when Saudi Arabia banned oil sales to the United States because of its alliance with Israel and support of Israel against Arab states. This was done in response to the United States' support of Israel against Arab states. As a result of OPEC's manipulation of oil prices and its competition with producers from non-OPEC countries, oil prices increased in 1980, and Saudi Arabia's earnings from oil exports increased along with it. The fluctuations in oil price, together with the sanctions imposed by the United States on Iraq about its oil exports, led to an increase in the amount of oil sent by Saudi Arabia to the United States. After then, the two nations continued their partnership on energy matters and maintaining security. The United States maintained a military presence in Saudi Arabia for an extended length of time and provided the country's authorities with advice on military strategy.

Due to strategic coordination between Saudi Arabia and the United States, with a significant emphasis on reducing Iran's regional influence, the United States is the largest supplier of military equipment to Saudi Arabia. Saudi Arabia also appears to have strategic coordination with Israel. Delaney (2009) suggests that the government of Saudi Arabia has long attempted to find a balance between its position as a regional powerhouse in the Arab world and its strong ties to the United States of

America. Throughout their relationship, both countries have conducted business traditionally and it has always revolved around national defense and oil production issues. In 1951, Gause (1994) states that the Military Alliance Assistance Agreement came into existence, enabling the United States to trade weapons with Saudi Arabia and establish a weapons training mission in Saudi Arabia. As a consequence, the level of cooperation that existed between the two nations flourished during the 1960s.

A change in the government in Saudi Arabia, presented challenges for the alliance that the two nations shared when in July 1964, following a quarrel with his older brother Saud, who had previously served as monarch, Faisal was crowned king. However, he continued to work with the United States until October 20, 1973, when he advocated an import restriction on the Americas and Europe in favor of the Arab position (Blanchard, 2017). Even though there was a ban on oil exports, Saudi Arabia still faces an energy crisis. According to McDowall (2013), Faisal made the following comment during an interview with reporters from all over the world: "America's unconditional support of Israel against the Arabs makes it highly impossible to continue supplying the United States with oil, or even be friends with the United States" (McDowall, 2013).

As a result of Saudi Arabia's growing oil production and support for anti-communism, both countries developed closer relations. The Saudis acquired substantial quantities of American military hardware because of the funds that resulted from price increases. Friedman (2013) writes that these factors contributed to the development of closer ties between the two countries. As a direct result of this, the United States insisted on holding conversations with Syrians over the Golan Heights in March of 1974; following these discussions, the embargo was lifted. Later,

Washington and Riyadh agreed to expand their economic and military collaboration. During the 1975 fiscal year, the two countries negotiated \$2 billion in military contracts, including one that called for the supply of Saudi Arabia with sixty fighter planes. During this time, the two countries also agreed to expand their economic and military collaboration. In addition, to assist the United States in achieving its objectives, Saudi Arabians attempted throughout the 1970s to keep OPEC prices at a lower level than Iraq and Iran had hoped for. As an additional anti-communist military action, the United States began delivering F-15 airplanes to Saudi Arabia in January 1979.

Furthermore, in response to the Kargil war started by the Syrian regime in 1990, President George W. Bush decided to station 5,000 American soldiers in Saudi Arabia. This move was made to further cement the armaments agreement in exchange for the oil contract. According to Rashid et al. (1992), the invasion of Kuwait by Iraq in August 1990 significantly strengthened the United States and Saudi Arabia's security relations during the Gulf War. This took place in the middle of the 1980s. The United States was concerned about the safety of Saudi Arabia because Saddam Hussein had ambitions to invade and take control of the region's oil riches. Horton (2016) noted that while Saddam Hussein announced his intention to invade the region, the United States and King Fahd of Saudi Arabia launched their war on Iraq at the same time (Horton,2016). In the light of this and the agreement with King Fahd, operation Desert Shield was instituted, and President Bush deployed American soldiers to Saudi Arabia to defend the nation from an invasion by Iraq (up to 543,000 ground troops by the end of the campaign). The objective of Desert Shield was also to defend Kuwait from an impending invasion by Iraqi forces. At the same time, Saudi

Arabia dispatched more than 100,000 troops to other allies to create partnerships with them (Gause, 2016). During the ground fight that was part of Operation Desert Storm, Iraqi soldiers were defeated over four days and since the end of the Gulf War in 1991, a total of 5,000 American troops have been stationed in Saudi Arabia; this number increased to 10,000 during the Iraq War in 2002. In addition, The Fifth Fleet, a U.S. Naval stronghold, with its headquarters in Bahrain, is responsible for ensuring the safety of the government's oil shipments through the Persian Gulf trade routes (Ryan, 2016).

During the terrorist incident on September 11, 2001, which involved 19 terrorists, including 15 Saudi nationals, ties between the United States and Saudi Arabia deteriorated. Because of the purported connections between the terrorists and Saudi Arabia, the assault affected the partnership between the nations and disrupted their oil for security pact. However, according to Long (2004), the disagreements between the nations were overcome, and Saudi Arabia collaborated with the United States to combat terrorists suspected of hiding in Saudi Arabia and reportedly involved in the crime. However, Long (2004) suggested that the assault was precipitated by the presence of American forces in Saudi Arabian territories, which resulted in the United States pulling its troops out of Saudi Arabia.

After the assassination of Saudi journalist Jamal Khashoggi, there was a flurry of reports suggesting that the long-standing relationship between the United States and Saudi Arabia was entering new territory; as McKay (2019) pointed out in a piece that he authored, what the assassination of Jamal Khashoggi has come down to is another monument to the seemingly unshakeable tenacity of the connection between the world's most dynamic democracy and the Middle East's largest absolute monarchy

for the past eighty years. Saudi Arabia, became the target of intense criticism from the world, finally admitted that the killing took place and pledged to bring to justice the people involved. Investigations carried out by several international intelligence services, including the CIA, throw the needle at Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman, a 33-year-old monarch recognized as the true authority behind the operation. However, Saudi Arabia was particularly concerned about protecting its ties with one nation: the United States. This is because the Al-Saud dynasty, which has ruled Saudi Arabia continuously since its establishment of the Kingdom in 1932, is primarily dependent on security assurances and promises made by the United States to intervene if the desert kingdom is invaded. The United States made these assurances and promises, and in return, they receive economic benefits and what amounts to acquiescence about the unpopularity and occasionally controversy of its policies regarding the Middle East.

According to Aghamohammadi and Omid (2018), the United States conducted a few different actions as a direct response to the assassination. To begin, they made threats to withdraw the visas of any Saudi citizens who were found to be involved. Additionally, according to commentators, Mohammad bin Salman was not permitted to visit Washington or speak directly with the administration of Trump. After that, Trump recommended nominating John Abizaid, a retired general in the United States Army, to the position of ambassador to Saudi Arabia. This helped to rebuild and strengthen the diplomatic connections that had been broken between the United States and Saudi Arabia. Also, in the wake of the murder of the journalist, Saudi Arabia appointed Princess Reema Bint Anwar Al Saud as the country's first female ambassador. This appointment further strengthened the alliance by paving the

way for women's rights in governance and establishing legal protections that ensure women are paid equally to males and that they are not subject to discrimination in the workplace. (Aghamohammadi & Omid, 2018).

The make-up of the Saudi-American alliance

In the theory of international relations, according to neoliberal institutionalism, politics and economics are inextricably linked. Cooperation is thus "necessary in an interdependent world." Unlike realists, Keohane believes that cooperation in an anarchic society is conceivable and may be done through international institutions, but only if "states have sufficient common interests" (Keohane and Martin, 1995). While realists think that alliances and institutions dissolve once their goals are met, neoliberal institutionalism contends that the reverse occurs. Furthermore, institutions are not static; they adapt and can serve new functions, but if an institution eventually fails to be helpful, it must cease to exist (Narine ,1998)

Bronson (2006) sheds more light on the concept of realism by analyzing coalitions' power and threat balances. It has been elucidated as occurring whenever two or more sovereign bodies collaborate to safeguard their respective populations. The relationship between the United States and Saudi Arabia is built on mutually beneficial principles. Over the course of many years, the countries have ignored both their shared benefits and their significant disparities. Mutualism is a concept used by Stephen Walt to describe international relationships in which both parties stand to profit. Walt (1994) asserted that commitment and mutual advantage are necessary to develop mutually beneficial relationships successfully. Walt (1994) proposed an additional idea, which was that "Contract arrangements are made in both states to use

or refrain from taking military action against particular other nations, whether or not other countries are officially mentioned, the use of armed force to preserve or promote the common good."

According to Prados (2003), both powerful and weak nations require security and income to function normally. Smither (1990) asserts that the necessity to build coalitions is based on individual nations' divergent opinions and requirements. Weak countries often create alliances to defend themselves from potential threats or address security concerns. Strong countries often unite to form a united front against other powerful nations or offset their might. During times of conflict, having the political and military support of one's allies is deemed necessary (Dwivedi, 2012).

The connection between Saudi Arabs and the United States is an example of a beneficial collaboration that provides advantages for both parties. While the United States remained a coalition member so it could continue to export oil, Saudi Arabia demanded that the United States provide it with security. These initiatives aim to maintain peace and security and to strengthen a rules-based system to provide major benefits for both sides.

The modification of the structure of the Saudi American alliance

It must be emphasized that the "oil for security" equation, which has had a significant impact on the coalition that comprises the Saudi-American relationship for a considerable amount of time, has experienced some minor adjustments. As a result of the discovery and production of crude oil in the United States, (also known as shale oil), the United States has decreased its reliance on oil imported from Saudi Arabia in the first half of the oil equation. The United States of America is dependent

on Saudi Arabia's prominent position in regulating petroleum costs on the world's demand for oil, even though Saudi oil has become less important in recent years. This is due to the belief that Saudi Arabia, which claims to have the world's most enormous oil resources, will significantly impact the world petroleum industry in the coming years.

Pivot to Asia was a policy started by Barack Obama and continued by Donald Trump. Through this campaign, the United States has steadily shifted its significant attention away from Asia, the second component of the safety equation. As a direct consequence of this decision, American soldiers were relocated from the Gulf region to the Pacific and Asian regions. Despite this development, certain strategic partnerships between the United States of America and Saudi Arabia have not been altered in any way. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia remains one of the major consumers of armaments from the United States. They also work together to protect electronic data and maintain maritime security. However, Moawad (2017) reiterated that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, despite the fact that they work with the U.S. on these issues are beginning to doubt the US safety system to defend its stability. This is due to two different factors: The United States' policy is to strengthen its allies' military capabilities to reduce the likelihood that they will require immediate help from the United States military. This is necessary for its coastal adjustment strategy, which eliminates the need for immediate military intervention in situations with little bearing on its fundamental advantages (Moawad, 2017).

The next factor to consider is the United States' economy's weakening position in the Middle East labor market due to the Arab Spring. As a result of the economic slump, Saudi Arabia was obligated to keep its options open while continuing its long-

standing and crucial partnership with the United States. For this reason, Saudi Arabia has established several coalitions with robust cultural and global controls. One example of this is the Arab collaboration in Yemen's "Activity Decisive Storm," the global coalition in contradiction of psychological oppression that Saudi Arabia proclaimed in December 2015 with the backing of the quartet, thirty-four Arab, Asian, and African nations coalitions in contradiction of Qatar in June 2017. (Miller, 2017). In addition, Saudi Arabia has strengthened its relationships with several European nations, including Russia and China. Even though the foundational principles of the Saudi -American coalition have undergone a transition, the evolution of the transformation has not progressed to the point where it might cause the existing cooperative alliance between both countries to deteriorate or fail.

A synopsis of the research on the relevant literature

According to the conclusions of an inquiry into the growth of the Saudi-American alliance and the barriers it has experienced, both nations have faced significant obstacles and issues. In the past, conflicts and impediments were rooted in the fact that both nations practice various religions, regional religions, have substantial cultural differences, and several other factors. The fact that both nations have different perspectives on a number of global issues is a major cause of disagreement between them and has weakened their alliance. To mention a few, these include the government transition in Egypt, the nuclear deal with Iran, the civil war in Syria, and freedom and human rights problems (Aziz,2019). Despite all these, the governments of Saudi Arabia and the United States have reconciled their differences and enjoyed good bilateral ties, including close security cooperation, a strong relationship to combating terrorism, a symbolic pledge to cooperate during times of

regional unrest, a continuous trade partnership, and a significant number of foreign students from Saudi Arabia to the United States. Thus, it can be phronetically deduced that the alliances continue because of their reliance on prior achievements as focus points to justify further collaboration and partnership.

CHAPTER 3- RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

What is the research methodology?

Knowledge is increased via research. According to Bhattacharjee (2012), there are three categories of scientific research projects that may be classified according to the goals of the investigation: explanatory, descriptive, and exploratory.

Bhattacharjee(2012) explains that explanatory research seeks explanations of observed phenomena, problems, or behaviors. It searches for answers to why and how questions, whereas descriptive analysis looks at the phenomenon's what, where, and when. By identifying the causes and effects of the target phenomena, it aims to connect the dots in research. Examples include comprehending the causes of juvenile criminality or gang violence to prescribe solutions to such societal ills. According to Bhattacharjee (2012), most academic or doctoral research belong to the explanatory category.

On the other hand, descriptive research aims to make thorough observations and documentation of exciting phenomena. These observations must follow the scientific method (i.e., be repeatable, precise, etc.), making them more trustworthy than random observations made by untrained individuals. An example of descriptive research includes the tabulation of employment statistics by the Bureau of Labor, which uses similar instruments for estimating employment by sector, population growth, and ethnicity over multiple employment surveys. The aim is to allow readers to make an objective before-and-after comparison regarding population or employment trends (Bhattacharjee,2012).

Exploratory research is frequently carried out in new areas of inquiry, with the goals being to scope out the size or extent of a specific phenomenon or generate some

initial theories about that phenomenon and test the viability of conducting a more in-depth study about it. For instance, exploratory research may focus on determining the degree of citizens' dissatisfaction with government policies during an economic recession. It may attempt to understand how it manifests, the frequency of public protests, and the presumed causes of such discontent, such as ineffective government policies dealing with inflation, interest rates, or unemployment (Bhattacharjee,2012). Furthermore, exploratory research thoroughly evaluates several sources of information to analyze, draw insights, and arrive at firm conclusions.

Saunders et al. (2019) note that effective research selects the most innovative and relatable materials from various research methodology options. The method is fundamental for emphasizing the validity and reliability of the research paper. The research methodology will highlight the techniques through which the research problem is investigated; the methodology will also provide the rationale for the selected research approaches. Each process and procedures correspond to a different system in the research study.

Research Paradigm

As described by Saunders et al. (2019), research consists of various stages and levels to be completed in sequential order. The current research study follows an interpretivism philosophy and epistemological paradigm. The interpretivism philosophical approach helps portray the information in a comprehensive manner, and this paradigm is congruent with the descriptive and constructive research orientations. The purpose of this study is to investigate the diplomatic ties that exist between Saudi Arabia and the United States. As a result, the chronological progression of their connection will be emphasized, along with forecasts regarding the future.

Research strategy

This research qualifies as an entirely new investigation, yet one that draws on previously published findings. Furthermore, it is non-empirical research based on a systematic review of published and related publications. The study will examine previous literature to see how Saudi Arabia and the United States have interacted in the past and how this association has evolved. Non-empirical research has been employed to systematically evaluate the existing literature to conduct a complete study of Saudi-U.S ties and determine the current relationship's strengths and flaws. The systematic literature review (SLR) identifies and evaluates appropriate sources of information to find out the answers to the research questions that are set (Dewey & Drahota, 2016). With this technique for assessing sources to provide solutions, the criteria for a systematic literature review are predetermined. In a systematic literature review, a wide range of study types are rigorously analyzed to identify trends or underlying factors. Thus, analysis and prediction of the future of Saudi-US relations can be improved by determining and identifying these trends.

Research method

Saunders et al. (2019) posit that research studies may utilize qualitative or quantitative approaches to data collection and analysis. The methodologies of the study are selected with consideration given to the requirements and characteristics of the research objectives to meet the needs of the study. The qualitative method is relevant for the Interpretivism philosophy and comprehensive or descriptive analysis. Since qualitative research does not include the quantitative measurement and examination of the sample, it is ideally suited for use in studies with relatively small sample sizes. According to Collis and Hussey (2003), the qualitative approach to

research provides a comprehensive description and analysis of the topic under investigation without limiting or confining the overall scope of the study. However, it has also been stated that the benefits and effectiveness of qualitative research are more readily acquired through the talents and capabilities of the researcher. A firm stance was adopted to eliminate the risk of bias, and topics were separated into subheadings in addition to regular feedback from learned colleagues.

	Qualitative	Quantitative
Conceptual	Concerned with the informant's perspective on human behavior	Investigating social phenomena to identify facts.
	Assumes a constantly changing and negotiated reality	Assumes a constant and quantifiable reality
Methodological	Data is collected through participant observation and interviews	Data is collected through quantifiable things
	Data is analyzed by themes based on descriptions provided by informants.	Data is analyzed through numerical comparisons and statistical conclusions
	Data is reported in the language of The informant	Data is reported using statistical analysis

(Minichiello et al 1990)

Figure 1: Differences between Qualitative and Quantitative methods

Research approach

According to DeMichele (2018), research approaches can be divided into deductive, inductive, and abductive reasoning. Deductive reasoning is all about certainties. It works "down" from specific rules and facts to conclusions that are logically certain and must follow the premises of an argument. It is a way to look at things similar to rationalism as examines what is logically valid and must be true about a system. DeMichele(2018) noted that it is often called "top-down reasoning" because it usually starts with a general statement and then explains why it is true. Abductive reasoning is a type of logic that is utilized in the process of formulating a hypothesis for subsequent testing. It entails reasoning toward probable conclusions based on an informed judgment as to what those conclusions may be.

(DeMichele,2018)

The inductive research approach was selected as the methodology of choice for this study. DeMichele summarizes the three approaches - abduction refers to the process of formulating a hypothesis. Induction on the other hand,refers to the analysis of the data obtained from testing a theory, and deduction refers to the process of deriving specific logical conclusions based on the facts collected. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2005), an inductive method begins with a particular observation, which is then translated into hypotheses or conclusions based on observations. Because it identifies the active region of the study context and is extremely good for evaluating tiny samples and extensive research, the inductive approach was chosen to be utilized in this investigation because it is the purpose for which it was designed. Furthermore, the inductive approach was chosen because it is qualitative research that attempts to make sense of or interpret phenomena in terms of the meanings ascribed to them (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005).

Data collection method

A non-empirical systematic literature review employing the qualitative technique will be used in this investigation. In non-empirical research, the study relies on inductive and deductive reasoning to theorize logical assumptions about the research subjects. Secondary research is also used in this study. In the book *Research Methods* by Chapman et al. (2005), two research methods are identified: primary and secondary. Primary research methods are employed to collect data firsthand by the researcher. This is achieved by applying research techniques such as questionnaires, interviews, or participant observation. Secondary research, also known as desk research, is a research method that involves compiling existing data sourced from a variety of channels. This covers internal and, more typically, external sources, such as data collected by the government, organizational bodies, and the internet (Chapman et al., 2005).

Secondary research is available in various formats, including published statistics, reports, and survey answers. The needed data may also be obtained via websites, libraries, and museums. Literature and official websites of the U.S. and Saudi governments will be used to acquire qualitative data. The literary sources will be drawn from periodicals and online libraries. There will be information on the US-Saudi relationship, economic cooperation between the two nations, and the influence of Saudi Vision 2030 on US-Saudi and how it ties with U.S. involvement.

Sample Selection

Showkat (2017) identifies two forms of sampling- probability and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling involves random selection, allowing the researcher to make solid statistical inferences about the whole group. Non-probability sampling involves non-random selection based on convenience or other criteria,

allowing for accessible data collection. The references used in the study were selected through purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling where researchers rely on their judgment about the relevance and advantage of the chosen source for education. Other names for purposeful sampling include critical and accidental sampling. In this method, the researcher selects the references for critical analysis and result generation based on personal judgment. The research journals used provide comprehensive information about U.S. Saudi reliance and exhaustively provide a response to the research questions.

Data analysis

The current research study is opted to be secondary qualitative research in which the data collected from the secondary selected literature sources is analyzed through descriptive analysis. The researcher has decided on descriptive analysis so data can be analyzed and comprehensive, and answers can be provided to the research questions. According to Lawless and Heymann (2010), descriptive analysis is a type of analysis that helps in explaining and summarizing the facts of any given data in a constructive manner so that patterns and determinants can be discovered. Descriptive analysis can be used to help explain and summarize any data. It is an excellent instrument for working with qualitative data.

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that influence the post-oil relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States. The nature of this study has been designated as exploratory, and the overarching purpose is to investigate the connection that exists between Saudi Arabia and the United States in the context of Vision 2030. This will be accomplished by identifying the post-oil elements influencing the US-Saudi relationship. It will also highlight Saudi Arabia's policy tilt

toward the United States to seek more significant investments and strategic help from the United States in its effort to transition from an economy reliant on oil to a more flexible economy. By analyzing a wide variety of information sources, the research will unearth previously unknown material and come to findings on the subject. The qualitative research approach will be utilized to investigate the actions taken by both administrations and determine how they will affect the relationship between the two countries. The study will gain new insights and arrive at definitive conclusions on the topic by carefully assessing several different information sources. Additionally, because it is secondary research with data sourced from existing channels, inductive and deductive methods will be utilized to determine the relationship determinants based on the data obtained from the secondary sources.

CHAPTER 4—FINDINGS AND RESULT

The descriptive analysis of the above sources provides efficient information about the Saudi Vision 2030, its approaches, and the Saudi-US relationship. The review provided gives insight into Saudi-US relations, their background, conceptual framework, and determinants on which the relationship has been maintained through decades.

US and Saudi Arabia relationship determinants

Saudi Arabia and the United States have a history of cooperation on security issues. According to Blanchard (2018), Saudi Arabia and the United States have maintained a long-term relationship based on oil and arms deals. The study presented by Aziz (2019) indicated that Saudi Arabia plays the role of the largest customer of US arms and foreign military sales (FMS). Thus, Saudi Arabia is the biggest consumer of FMS from the US. Three important Saudi Arabian security assistance organizations—"the Ministry of Defense, the National Guard, and the Ministry of Interior"—have constantly received support from the United States via FMS. The US Army Corps of Engineers has also been essential to Saudi Arabian to build projects, both military and civilian, since the 1950s (Aziz, 2019).

According to Blanchard (2017), the US administration considers the Saudi government an essential partner. US arms sales and associated security cooperation programs have continued with congressional monitoring and some congressional opposition. However, from FY2009 through FY2016, the US and Saudi Arabia signed official military sales deals totaling more than \$65 billion. Since 2015, the US-trained Saudi military has supported military operations in Yemen with US-origin equipment,

logistical support, and shared information (Blanchard,2017). In addition to arms deals, the United States collaborates with the Saudi Arabian government to give technical assistance in fields like economic development, trade, and education. Also, deep commercial ties exist between the US and Saudi Arabia. Saudi Arabia's second-largest trading partner is the United States, which is also one of Saudi Arabia's biggest trading partners in the Middle East. With around 500,000 barrels of oil supplied to the American market daily, Saudi Arabia ranks third among the countries from which the United States imports its oil (Aziz, 2019).

In 2016, a trade contract was signed between Saudi Arabia and the US. In the same year, Saudi Arabia also launched its Saudi vision 2030 program. This program was launched to enhance and improve the economic conditional and dependency of the Saudi Arabia. Apart from direct trade deals with the United States, Saudi Arabia is also active in the United Nations (UN), International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, and World Trade Organization (WTO). The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is also an observer to the Organization of American States (Blanchard, 2018).

How Saudi Vision 2030 will transform Saudi Arabia's economy

Saudi Vision 2030 is a national sociopolitical and economic reform aimed at reducing Saudi Arabia's dependency on crude oil through economic diversification and the growth of many public services. The primary objectives are to increase the share of non-oil commercial sectors like tourism, banking, and information technology, and to project an open-minded and secular national image worldwide. The plan's actual aims include afforestation, expanding the extent of protected areas, lowering emissions, diversifying the economy to be less dependent on oil, and constructing a future metropolis powered entirely by renewable energy.

Faudot (2019) suggests that Saudi Vision 2030 is the most significant achievement of Crown Prince Salman, the reigning monarch of the Saud dynasty. Before this, the country had only made a few reforms or events. In 2015, Mohammed bin Salman assumed the throne, and under his reign, the economic growth rate was observed to decrease from 1.7% to 0.1% within a year. The industrial growth rate also suffered. It declined by 0.3% in 2017. Faudot (2019) claimed that the economic decline caused unemployment in the country, which increased to 12.8%.

The Saudi Vision 2030 is based on three major themes: a dynamic society, a thriving economy, and a bold country. According to Lee (2021), to achieve a dynamic society, according to Vision 2030, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia will focus on its people and the Islamic faith through a series of commitments to tourism, heritage sites, entertainment, and health. In addition, to build a thriving economy, there are plans to focus on the diversification of the economy to generate dynamic work possibilities for the citizens. There would be an exceptional focus on education, entrepreneurship, manufacturing, renewable energy, and commerce. The third theme of Vision 2030 plans to emphasize responsibility, openness, and effectiveness. To achieve this, the Kingdom prepares to implement a zero-tolerance policy for all levels of corruption, increase transparency by expanding online services and improving governance standards, while also bolstering the non-profit sector through increased efficiency and impact (Lee ,2021)

Faudot (2019), further writes that the Saudi Vision 2030 seems promising. However, the odds of the vision's success are stacked against it since implementing the principles and policies of the Saudi Vision 2030 necessitates successful modernization in the kingdom, and many government systems are outdated. The failure of the vision

might spuriously indicate the kingdom's inability to deal with unemployment, young job prospects, and a welfare-supported social compact.

Also, the failure of the vision may present problems with distributing financial aid to Saudi nationals. The Saudi Vision 2030 is projected to reduce reliance on oil, but there is a strong need to improve other industries for revenue and economic growth. It creates possibility that the country would face a dilemma if its reliance on oil is reduced and there is no financial gain from other avenues. Saudi citizens are offered aid by their government and the failure of the vision might dampen the common people's expectations and potentially harm the country's foreign relations. According to Moshashai et al (2020), the failure of Saudi Vision 2030 will cause instability in the kingdom and in Saudi Arabia's neighboring countries.

Vision 2030 and foreign relations

The Saudi Vision 2030 was initiated to enhance the infrastructure and ensure the economy is less reliant on the sales on oil. The Vision was launched with the international community in mind. Its successful execution and success is expected to enhance foreign relations. A portion of the vision's aim is to achieve a progressive economic growth rate for the Kingdom, which is projected to require an environment that attracts the necessary skills and capabilities from within and beyond the national borders. To this end, there is a provision in the plans to improve living and working conditions for non-Saudis, by extending the ability of expatriates to own real estate in certain areas, thereby enhancing the quality of life, permitting the establishment of more private schools, and adopting a practical and simple system for issuing visas and residence permits. The goal is to attract foreign investment, which is projected to boost economic development and attract additional foreign investment.

Also, the outlook of the Saudi government on the involvement of women in day-to-day activities is another attractive feature of Vision 2030 that makes it appealing to foreign relations. Hence, the encouragement of women in education and the initiative to invest in their productive capabilities and enable them to strengthen their future and contribute to the development of our society and economy is another checkpoint in Vision 2030.

According to Cafiero et al. (2019), given the project's magnitude, the Saudi Vision 2030 objectives can only be executed with appropriate foreign investment. Hence the visits by the crown prince to solicit support from the United States and France to secure Western investment. In a release on the Saudi website, it was noted that the United States is assisting Saudi Arabia in pursuing the challenging objectives of Vision 2030 in the same spirit of collaboration that has long been a cornerstone of U.S.-Saudi relations. Americans and Saudis currently cooperate in every industry, working together to study, research, and, more lately, act in movies and engage in concerts and sporting events. This relationship generates \$54 billion in commerce and investment between the US and Saudi Arabia annually. In addition, the economic change of Saudi Arabia under Vision 2030 has been significantly aided by American businesses.

Besides western investments, Mohamed Bin Salman's visit to China and Japan emphasizes the importance of establishing and maintaining economic relations with the world's major economies to achieve the Kingdom's ambitious domestic agenda. Cafiero et al. (2019) noted that the House of Saud is looking for sources of finance in every corner of the globe; hence, unfettered foreign relations are essential for the project's success and beyond.

Other determinants of the US-Saudi relationship

In 2016, Saudi Arabia executed forty-seven individuals, including dissident Shia cleric Nimr Baqr al-Nimr. This act appeared to be a premeditated attempt to inflame tensions in the Middle East and, it incited doubts as to why America is an ally of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The agreement was military protection for Saudi Arabia in exchange for a steady oil supply, pricing of oil in US dollars, and Saudi support for US foreign policy activities across the world. Although, recently, the partnership has moved in recent years from "oil for security" to one based on regional prosperity, food and energy security, stability, and climate change.

However, during the Cold War, it became more important to combat communism and maintain a political status quo in the Middle East that seemed to suit the interests of both nations. In the light of that, the 70-year partnership has caused the United States to turn a blind eye to Saudi Arabia's violations of human rights and its theocratic, authoritarian regime, which are opposed to American principles. Although, Saudi Arabia's recent actions are not unprecedented, they highlight some essential strains in the US-Saudi partnership-the origin was based on oil-the Saudi royals gave the American oil corporation Standard Oil exclusive drilling rights in the eastern province of the nation in 1933. The combined US-Saudi business, which would become known as ARAMCO (Arabia American Oil Company), discovered massive deposits in 1938. During World War II, when the United States was in critical need of petroleum, the government intended to safeguard the investments of American businesses.

Thereafter, the Saudis began lobbying for a more prominent involvement in ARAMCO after the war, and they were finally able to take control of the company.

Nevertheless, they did not officially nationalize it until 1980. Despite the United States' diminishing direct participation in Saudi Arabia's oil industry, the partnership between the two countries grew stronger. This is because both nations believed that the influence of the Soviet Union in the Middle East was the most critical problem facing the area at the time. The Saudi Arabian government can be described as a monarchy and a theocracy. The policy of the Soviet Union of supporting Marxist and nationalist movements in the Middle East posed a direct threat to both halves of the Saudi government. The monarchs feared leftist revolutionary sentiment, while the Wahhabis loathed Soviet secularism. Both halves of the Saudi government feared Soviet secularism. Because of the structure of the Saudi system, the country was destined to be a natural antagonist of communism in the Soviet Union.

Hence, the United States of America and Saudi Arabia evolved their original oil partnership into a broader security alliance to work together against a common adversary. Both nations signed their first official military pact, the Mutual Defense Assistance Agreement in 1951, which included provisions for supplying American armaments to Saudi Arabia and training Saudi soldiers by American forces. This was the first time the two countries had collaborated on their respective militaries.

In addition, the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in 1979 was arguably the most significant event during the Cold War era for this partnership. Saudi officials feared this would mark the beginning of a more significant Soviet assault on the region. The United States regarded this as a chance to snare its adversary in a conflict of its own in Vietnam. Secretly, the two nations supplied the anti-Soviet mujahideen rebels with weaponry. To aid armed, anti-American Islamic fanatics, the United States and Saudi

Arabia each contributed at least \$3 billion and the two nations' intelligence agencies also needed to work closely together.

The post-oil reform relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States

In relation to the United States, the oil reform initiative, which began in 2016, has had the most significant influence on Saudi Arabia's relationship with the United States. Mutual aims exist between the two countries-the commitment to regional stability and counterterrorism measures, stability of oil prices and an attempt to confront a common enemy during the cold war (the Soviet Union). These have been the determinants of the U.S -Saudi Arabia relations. Also, the tensions in recent history between the two states that has been the cause of friction between the two nations, notably Saudi Arabia's human rights record and its role in the Yemeni civil war.

However, the oil reform process has significantly molded Saudi Arabia's post-oil reform relationship with the United States. The reform effort, which began in 2016, aimed to wean Saudi Arabia's economy off its reliance on oil earnings. The process has been gradual, with various setbacks, but it is still considered a top priority for the Saudi government. The United States has backed the reform process and provided Saudi Arabia with technical aid. However, there have been questions regarding the speed of reform and the Saudi government's capacity to implement the reforms. The research was also able to identify that the Oil reforms in the form of Saudi Vision 2030 plan, might be a way for the United States to be rid of Saudi Arabia and other middle Eastern allies or and/or an opportunity for the United States to extend its influence in the Middle east.

Tensions over Saudi Arabia's human rights record have also strained relations with the United States. Saudi Arabia's leadership has been chastised for its treatment of women, minorities, and political dissidents. The murder of journalist Jamal Khashoggi in October 2018 brought these concerns to the forefront (Koleilat, 2021). The United States has also denounced Saudi Arabia's involvement in Yemen's civil war. In 2014, a coalition led by Saudi Arabia intervened to assist the world-renowned government in fighting Houthi rebels, initiating the conflict. Because of the humanitarian crisis caused by the conflict, about 24 million people require assistance. The US has requested a cease-fire and peace negotiations to end the crisis (Koleilat, 2021). Despite these tensions, the relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States remains strong. As a result, the United States remains Saudi Arabia's closest ally, and the two countries continue to collaborate on several common challenges.

How Saudi Vision 2030 will affect U.S-Saudi relations

With respect to Saudi Vision 2030 and the United States, in a report released by the white house on 15 July 2022, the United States applauded the Kingdom's Vision 2030, a plan for radical economic and social change that included measures to empower women in the workforce and foster religious tolerance. For mutual advantage, Saudi Arabia encouraged more private U.S. investment in the Kingdom and more Saudi investment in the United States. According to Harrs (2019), the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 initiative to reform its economy and society will have a substantial impact on the United States' capacity to confront and counter Iran. Vision 2030, whether successful or not, would shift the balance of power in the Middle East, benefiting either a strong American ally (Saudi Arabia) or the most

formidable and long-standing US enemy in the area (Iran). This is because both areas continue a heated struggle for regional and Islamic domination. According to Hass (2019), Iran, since the Islamic Revolution in 1979, serves as the principal regional challenge and adversary to the US, while the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in many respects, acts as the core of US attempts to resist and degrade Iranian influence in the area. Whether Vision2030 succeeds or fails, the sheer magnitude and size of its intended impacts will define the momentum of America's ongoing struggle with Iran and may play a key part in determining who retains control in the Middle East.

On an ideological level, Hass (2019) believes that if Vision2030 succeeds in introducing Western values that contribute to a balanced and prosperous economy as well as a foreigner-friendly open society, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia will immediately serve as a model for other Middle Eastern societies plagued by government corruption, limited economic opportunities, and social restrictions. On an economic level, the achievement of Vision 2030 may reduce the Islamic Republic of Iran's economic capabilities because of the intended international investment into the KSA because of Vision2030. It will also probably entice traditional Iranian economic partners to reinvest in a more open and friendlier KSA market. This potential economic success may make it more difficult for the Iranians to avoid US economic sanctions meant to pressure them into abandoning hostile policies against American interests.

However, Koduvayur (2018) has a distinctive point of view on this topic. In a cable news network report, she mentioned that some aspects of the strategic cooperation between the United States and Saudi Arabia are still critical to the interests of the United States, most notably Riyadh's position as the world's swing oil

producer. The enormous oil wealth held by the monarchy helps maintain stability in oil markets worldwide and keeps prices at a reasonable level. And now that the Saudis have unveiled their Vision 2030 to become less dependent on oil, it is an opportunity for the United States to distance itself from its unhappy marriage with Saudi Arabia. Specifically, an opportunity for the United States to end its military alliance with Saudi Arabia.

According to Koduvayur (2018), the United States of America has to develop a national plan for a post-oil future, or else Washington would be unable to move forward and remain mired in the past. According to the report, a national strategy for a post-oil lot would increase the United States' geopolitical flexibility and power across the world, eliminating the country's requirement to rely on less-than-ideal allies. A plan of this kind would make it possible for the United States to pursue its interests and ideals in equal measure, ultimately resolving Washington's decades-long conundrum with the Saudis and its other Middle Eastern friends.

The scope and approach of the Saudi Vision 2030

The Saudi Vision 2030 is a plan of action to lessen Saudi Arabia's reliance on oil, diversify its economy, and expand public service areas including health, education, infrastructure, leisure, and tourism. Three main pillars support Saudi Vision 2030. The position of Saudi Arabia as the spiritual and political epicenter of the Arab and Islamic nations serves as the foundation of the first pillar. This is the motivation behind the goal of elevating its status as a historic site. The second pillar of the vision is to make the nation a global investment powerhouse, allowing the country to

capitalize on its investment capabilities, stimulate the economy, and diversify revenue streams.

The third component of the vision is the transformation of the geographically advantageous position of the country into a worldwide center that connects three continents, namely Asia, Europe, and Africa. As a result, the geographic location will be between vital global waterways, transforming the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia into a commercial hub and a gateway to the rest of the world. In addition, measures are in place to bolster and diversify the capacities of the economy, transforming critical strengths into instruments that will enable a genuinely diversified future. To this end, there are plans to change ARAMCO (Arabia America Oil) from a simple oil-producing company into a multinational industrial conglomerate worldwide.

The impacts of the Saudi vision on the Saudi Arabia's oil-dependent economy

The study identified the goal of the Vision 2030 as an avenue to reduce dependence on oil income and develop various facets of the government and economy. In addition, there are plans to commence domestic manufacture of military armaments in a bid to provide the country's armed forces with the most advanced machinery and equipment available. At the same time, increase the number of job opportunities available to citizens and maintain a more significant proportion of the nation's resources within its borders. Furthermore, for government establishments, there are plans to increase the number of digital services available to decrease wait times and cut back on cumbersome bureaucracy while executing strategies to adopt comprehensive transparency and accountability reforms to evaluate the performance of government agencies and hold them accountable for any shortcomings.

CHAPTER 5- CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This research has attempted to study and distinguish the determinants of the Saudi-US relationship post-oil changes. The kingdom of Saudi Arabia, established in 1932 has been ruled by the Al Saud family and possesses considerable sway on the international stage due to its vast oil reserves and being the birthplace of the Islamic faith. The exploratory study identified subtleties on the difficulties the two nations encountered, their relationship history, and the effect Saudi vision 2030 will have on US-Saudi relations? Through non-empirical research and systematic literature review, the study has been able to analyze the following objectives which are

- To critically analyze the scope and approach of the Saudi Vision 2030
- To evaluate the impacts of the Saudi vision on the Saudi Arabia's oil-dependent economy
- To study the post-oil reform relationship between Saudi Arabia and the United States.

The conclusion contains the key findings of the research study.

Saudi Arabia's economy depends on its oil income. The country has been one of the greatest oil exporters among gulf countries. The nation is subject to oil incomes which make up to 90% of the money-related worth of the economy of the country. Studies have proposed that Saudi Arabia needs to upgrade its dependence on oil hence the Vision 2030 project. Even though the USA and Saudi Arabia share no social, moral or religious framework. Saudi Arabia and the United States have reciprocal relations in which both sides benefit. Although the relations between the two

countries have experienced difficulties, it is founded on mutualism because both nations benefit from the partnership.

The groundwork of the Saudi-US collusion was laid by President Franklin Roosevelt and King Abdul Aziz in 1945. The relationship endured the 1973 oil ban and, surprisingly, the 9/11 assault and bounced back from the Khashoggi murder amid boundless clamor over the conflict in Yemen. It has been established that the United States maintains strong defense and security ties with Saudi Arabia, supported by ongoing high-value weapon sales, critical infrastructure security cooperation, and counterterrorism initiatives. These ties are supported by long-standing military training programs that have been in place for quite some time which either party would have a tough time breaking or replacing and would find very expensive to undertake. Even though Saudi and American officials have taken steps to maintain and deepen these ties, differences in preferred strategies and methods may continue to complicate bilateral coordination on regional security issues. These differences may include action against Iran as well as action against the Islamic State and other terrorist groups. However, the study identified that an increased willingness on the part of the United States to arm and train Saudi security forces may reduce the potential burdens placed on United States forces, but it may also further entangle the United States in predicaments or disputes in situations in which Saudi forces equipped or trained by the United States are deployed.

MAJOR RESEARCH FINDINGS

The research study has analyzed the challenges and opportunities of the Saudi-US relationship. The current study has revealed the challenges and the determinants that

can affect their relationship in the future. The research findings can be summed up into the following points.

- Saudi Arab and the United States have maintained bilateral relations since their alliance establishment.
- The alliance between the countries is based on the mutual benefits of oil for security formula.
- Since their alliance, the countries have encountered several challenges. However, analysis observed that these challenges did not negatively impact or influence the countries' relations.
- Apart from the security and the oil interest, the more common claims of Saudi Arabia and the United States are maintaining reasonable oil prices in the international market, counterterrorism and, curbing Iranian influence.
- Saudi Arabia is very focused on balancing its strategic relationship with the United States to achieve sustainability among the regional threats and crises. The strategic relation of Saudi Arabia with the United States can aid the country in gaining superiority in the Gulf region and the oil trade.
- On the other hand, the US is keen to maintain strategic relations with Saudi Arabs because Saudi Arabia has proven to be a reliable ally in the energy market and in countering terrorism.
- The alliance of Saudi Arabia and the United States encountered terrorism attacks, 9/11, and differences of opinion in the Arab spring. However, still, the countries managed good relations due to tremendous interest in the benefits.
- Saudi Arabia and the United States sometimes practice transactional relationships because the US demands compensation for the security it

provides. The transaction relations approach has enhanced Saudi Arabia and initiated cooperation with countries like China and Russia.

- However, it is observed that it is difficult for Saudi Arabia to find a strategic ally other than the United States in the foreseeable future. This is because both countries already have a history and an established mutual understanding.

Limitations of the research

The topic of this study is quite broad and has enough information to supply facts and increase understanding of the connection between Saudi Arabia and the United States. However, research endeavors may or may not encounter obstacles during critical examination, data collection, or analysis. In this study, shortlisting the most valuable sources was a complicated task. All the same, the current study aims to successfully preempt the future of Saudi-US relations.

This study aims to anticipate the future of Saudi-US relations and identify its determinants. Because various unknown external forces influence international relations, making accurate predictions is impossible. As a result, aspects of the Saudi-US connection are beyond this research's purview, but future research material might contribute to a deeper understanding of the relationship between the two nations.

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